

A Study on the Role of Non-Government Organization's in Protecting Consumer Rights

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Introduction :

NGO's play a major role in paving way for the protection and promotion of consumers. They educate consumers by conducting training programmes, workshops and publishing journals. The NGO makes the consumer aware of the legal remedy available for consumer protection. Though not expressly mentioned anywhere, the philosophy of consumer justice is permeated and reverberated through the Preamble, Fundamental rights and Directive Principles of State Policy of the Indian Constitution. The aim of consumer justice is to ensure that the consumer gets what he has paid for in quality and in right measure. The most effective method, for safeguarding the consumers' interest is not only in the state intervention, but also in active participation of the NGOs.

Concept of NGO :

A non-governmental organization (NGO) is a non-profit group that functions independently of any government. NGOs, sometimes called civil societies,

are organized on community, national and international levels to serve a social or political goal such as humanitarian causes or the environment. Non-governmental organizations are those organizations which aim at promoting the welfare of the people and which are non-profit making. They have voluntary decision-making structure, and are free from the interference of the government. They may be fully or partially financed by the government or any other financial agency. However, the NGOs have to abide by the rules provided in the government regulations regarding them.

Activities under taken by NGO's in protection of consumer rights :

- **Exploration :** The problems of consumers are solved by conducting extensive research and surveys. Study is conducted to identify malpractices in the products. Intensive market surveys are performed and various tests are conducted. The organisation publish in their portal regarding their assessments. The complaints of the consumers are received and necessary actions for redressal are taken after proper analysis.
- **Opining :** The NGO's have members who are very much knowledgeable in legal aspects. People with very good experience are appointed. These people guide consumers regarding their problems and help them in solving their issues. Generally, consumers are not aware of the laws existing in the country for their welfare. NGO's help in educating the consumers regarding the provisions they have regarding redressed.
- **Complaint Filing :** They help in filing complaints against the organizations which provide injustice to the consumers. NGO's help in filing petitions in the court. They act as a medium in order to get justice for deprived consumers.
- **Meetings :** Regular meetings are conducted to create awareness. Consumers attend the meeting and discuss the problems faced by them on a regular basis. The meeting will be conducted in a democratic manner, in the sense that all of them will be given a opportunity to pool their vies. And ideas and suggestions given by them are recorded and used for future purposes.
- **Print Media :** The NGO's use print media by means of flyers, brochures and advertisements in order to educate consumers. They try to educate the consumers regarding the rights and responsibilities in relation to the products and services.

- **Protesting** : The NGO's help by conducting protests for variety of reasons. They include food adulteration, rising price of the products for unnecessary reasons, when the products sold are underweight or when the consumers are sold with damaged products. They help in addressing consumer issues and solving the problems for their welfare.
- **Counseling** : A few members of an organization who are well conversant with the legal provisions under the various acts of interest provide legal help to affected consumers. They also handle public interest cases and symbolize the community in need of such legal assist and representation.
- **Testing the Quality** : NGO's conduct quality tests for variety of products and release the results to the consumers. This helps the consumers in knowing which product is of good quality. Sometimes quality of products help in alerting the consumers on the ill effects of the chemicals and other stuffs added in the products.

Consumer Associations of India :

NGOs dealing with the consumers' grievances, known as the consumer associations in India were first established in the 1960s. The first association to be set up was the Indian Association of Consumers. It was financed by the planning commission. In 1963, the National Consumer Association was set up. It was a wing of a social organization, the Bharat Sevak Samaj. Food crisis gave rise to rampant black-marketing in the 1960s. In 1964, the National Consumer Association started the movement against the price rise caused due to the drought of the 1960s. It used to hold meetings to protest against the price rise and formed social squads to keep a watch on the price trends in different cities of India.

Consequent to unfair trade practices followed by the traders, a consumer conference was held in 1974. To deal with the corrupt traders the Government of India passed Maintenance of Internal Security Act, 1971, Prevention of Black-marketing and Maintenance of Supplies of Essential Commodities Act, 1980.

The government set up in 1977 a committee, under the chairmanship of Justice Rajendra Sachar to "suggest the measures by which re-orientation of managerial outlook in the corporate sector could be brought about so as to ensure the

discharge of social responsibilities” by the business corporations. The Committee submitted its report in 1978 and suggested “corporate ethics” for corporate sector to make it socially responsible. It also recommended radical modification of MRTP act of 1969 and Indian Companies Act of 1956. As result of which Consumer Protection Act of 1986 was passed.

NGOs’ efforts in Redressal of Grievances :

- **Case against Indian Air Lines :**

Common cause filed a petition before the National Consumer Commission against the Indian Air Lines, Airport Authority of India and the Director General of Civil Aviation. The Complaint was filed against the alleged lack of attention to the safety of the aircrafts and the passenger travelling by the airlines; due to lack of facilities, and inconvenience caused the passengers in the delay of operation in flights.

- **Case of Inconvenience Caused in the Availability of Service :**

CUTS (Consumer Unity and Trust Society) a Calcutta based NGO filed a petition before the, National Consumer Commission alleging the inconvenience caused to the consumer due to the strike of the employees of Bank of Baroda who went on strike. The national commission declared the strike of the employees as “anti-consumer Acts. It directed the bank to see to it that the innocent consumers did not suffer. The commission hoped that the department of Banking and finance ministry, Government of India and RBI would urgently give attention to the matter of evolving some workable arrangements for rendering skeleton service.

- **Case of Adulterated Goods :**

Recently, CSE (Centre for science and environment) food researchers selected 13 brands of raw and processed honey, including Dabur, Patanjali, Baidyanath and Zandu, and subjected them to tests that are required under national food regulatory laws to be labeled as honey. The tests found adulteration in most brands. Amit Khurana, programme director of CSE’s Food Safety and Toxins team said “It shows how the business of adulteration has evolved so that it can pass the stipulated tests in India. We found that sugar

syrops are so designed that they can go undetected.” The investigation also uncovered that Indian companies in the business of honey were importing synthetic sugar syrups from China for adulterating with honey.

Suggestions :

The NGO’s should set certain principle when they are established. Political interference should be totally avoided. If politicians are involved, then the aim of the establishment will be of waste. It will be like a political party only. In the same way NGO’s should not get any bribes and mislead consumers. They should be fair in their evaluation and reveal what is true regarding the products. Publicity should be avoided. It is a service organisation, so if publicity comes then the purpose of the organisation will not be fulfilled. If a NGO is fair enough to reveal all details of the products, they should also be ready to face the consequences. They should have a high tolerance level and violence should be resorted at any case.

Conclusion :

The study aims in analysing the activities of NGO’s in consumer protection and several suggestions were provided for smooth functioning of Non-Government Organisations. We have seen that the non-governmental organisations have been playing important roles in the redressal of the consumer’s grievances. These problems arise due to the limited funds, lack of publicity, political interference, illiteracy of the masses; harassment by police and sometimes even non-cooperation by the people. In spite they continue to work unabated to establish justice in the society. Because a society can be the best only when justice prevails.

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